

Complexes of 2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)Benzthiazoline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

(MISS) K. DAS, S. K. GUPTA, U. S. PRASAD and L. K. MISHRA

Department of Chemistry, Science College, Patna-800 025

Manuscript received 17 September 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

Complexes of M^{2+} metal ion with 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)benzthiazoline (HOPBTZ) of formula $M(OPBTZ)_2$, ($M=Mn^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} or Pd^{2+}) have been prepared and characterised from the studies of magnetic susceptibility, uv and ir spectral measurements.

THE condensation product of *o*-aminobenzthiol with salicylaldehyde is not a stable Schiff base (A) as claimed by Dubey *et al*¹ rather it undergoes cyclization reaction forming 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)benzthiazoline (HOPBTZ) in good yield^{2,3}.

We are reporting here the preparation and characterisation of neutral inner chelates of Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II) with HOPBTZ.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by reported method⁴. It was used immediately after recrystallisation from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes :

$M(OPBTZ)_2$ ($M=Zn^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} or Cd^{2+}): An ethanolic solution of hydrated metal chloride (0.005 mol) was added to the ligand (0.01 mol) dissolved in hot ethanol (50-60 ml). From the resulting solution a small amount of impure product separated. The impure product was removed by filtration and the filtrate was made alkaline by adding excess of dilute ammonia when flocculent neutral complexes separated. The product was filtered, washed with dilute ammonia and dried *in vacuo* over $CaCl_2$.

$M(OPBTZ)_2$ ($M=Mn^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} or Pd^{2+}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal acetate (chloride in case of Pd^{2+}) was treated with the ligand in stoichiometric proportion. While stirring, the complex separated as granular precipitate. In case of copper the complex was obtained on diluting with excess of cold water. The product was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

The analytical results and magnetic moment values of the complexes are shown in Table 1. UV and ir spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier⁴.

TABLE 1

Complex	Colour	%Metal Found (Calcd.)	%Nitrogen Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M. (at 304°K)	Absorption band in ethanolic sol (cm ⁻¹)
Cu(OPBTZ) ₂	Dark green	12.03 (12.21)	5.42 (5.39)	1.88	25640
Ni(OPBTZ) ₂	Orange yellow	11.50 (11.39)	5.32 (5.44)	Dia.	14290-13330 23890
Pd(OPBTZ) ₂	Yellow	19.01 (18.86)	4.98 (4.96)	Dia.	—
Zn(OPBTZ) ₂	Cream white	12.86 (12.49)	5.12 (5.34)	Dia.	—
Mn(OPBTZ) ₂	Orange yellow	10.80 (10.69)	5.25 (5.46)	5.84	—
Cd(OPBTZ) ₂	Cream yellow	19.82 (20.15)	4.81 (4.91)	Dia.	—

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the complexes correspond with the formulae $[M(OPBTZ)_2]$ ($M=Zn^{2+}$, Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} or Pd^{2+}). The complexes are fairly soluble in ethanol, methanol and benzene but those of Pd(II), Mn(II) and Cu(II) are poorly soluble in ethanol and methanol but dissolve appreciably in DMF. The DMF solution of the complexes are non-conducting indicating their non-ionic nature. Ni(II), Pd(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes are diamagnetic but Cu(II) and Mn(II) complexes are paramagnetic at room temperature. The magnetic moment value of Cu(II) complex, *ca* 1.88 B.M., is similar to magnetically dilute Cu(II) complexes^{5,6} and of Mn(II) complex, *ca* 5.84 B.M., is similar to four or six coordinated high spin Mn(II) complexes⁷. The electronic absorption spectra of Mn(II), Zn(II), Pd(II) and Cd(II) complexes do not display absorption band in visible region.

The absorption spectrum of $[Ni(OPBTZ)_2]$ displays medium band at 21740 ($\epsilon_{max}=68$) assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition in planar field^{8,9} and a strong absorption below 25640 cm⁻¹, probably charge transfer type. Copper(II) complex displays a broad band in the region 14290-13330 cm⁻¹ and a strong absorption below 23890 cm⁻¹. The former is

assigned to $E_g \rightarrow T_{2g}$ transition and latter as charge transfer band¹⁰.

IR spectra : The ligand displays a number of bands located at 3233 m, 3023 w, 2850, 1600 m, 1575 s, 1460 m, 1451 s, 1420 sh, 1399 m, 1352 m, 1307 m, 1263 m, 1244 s, 1225 w, 1182 s, 1148 m, 1075 s, 1024 s, 920 s, 878 m, 852 w, 753 vs, 737 m, 715 m, 637 m, 575 m, 546 m, 510 m and 458 cm^{-1} due to various modes of ir vibrations of different groups present in the ligand molecules. The absence of band near $2400\text{-}2650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the absence of S-H group in the ligand molecule. A medium band at 3233 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration, which is shifted to lower wave number by $80\text{-}100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the bonding of ligand through benzthiazoline ring N-H nitrogen¹¹. A medium broad band at 2850 cm^{-1} is assigned as hydrogen bonded $\nu(\text{OH})$ vibration, which disappears in the complexes. The disappearance of the $\nu(\text{OH})$ band indicates the coordination of ligand through deprotonated phenolic OH. A medium band at 1352 cm^{-1} assigned as OH bending band¹² also disappears in almost all metal complexes. The (N-H) bending band of the ligand located at 1575 cm^{-1} is also shifted to lower wave number by $30\text{-}50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in its metal complexes supporting the involvement of N-H nitrogen in complexes. A medium band located at 1460 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ vibration. The $\nu(\text{C-O})$ band shifts to higher frequencies by $40\text{-}60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes. The shift

of $\nu(\text{C-O})$ band suggests the increase in bond order of phenolic (C-O) group on coordination^{13,14}. Since the ligand displays a number of bands in far ir region, definite frequency of (M-O) and (M-N) stretching bands could not be assigned.

References

1. K. P. DUBEY and SALEEM IFTIKHAR, "Proceeding Frontier in Coordination Chemistry", Allahabad, 1979.
2. R. G. CHARLES and H. FREISER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **18**, 422.
3. C. C. LEE, A. SYAMAL and L. J. THERIOT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1669.
4. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 547.
5. L. SACCONI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
6. E. FORSTER and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 823.
7. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 37.
8. B. BEHERA and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 372.
9. B. BOSNICH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 627.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
11. B. C. CURRAN, D. N. SEN, S. MUZISHIMA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 429.
12. T. J. LANE, I. NAKAGAWA, J. L. WALTER and A. J. KANDATHIL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 267.
13. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805.
14. C. M. HARRIS, H. R. H. PATIL and E. SINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1102.